

Pythagorean Neutrosophic Ideals in Semigroups

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Abstract. In this paper, we introduce the notion of Pythagorean neutrosophic ideals, Pythagorean neutrosophic bi-ideal, Pythagorean neutrosophic interior ideal, Pythagorean neutrosophic (1,2) ideal of semigroups and some of them interesting properties.

Keywords: Pythagorean fuzzy set; Neutrosophic set; fuzzy ideals; semigroup.

1. Introduction

After the introduction of the fuzzy set by Zadeh [11], several researchers conducted experiments on the generalizations of the notion of a fuzzy set. The concept of the intuitionistic fuzzy set was introduced by Atanassov [1,2] as a generalization of the fuzzy set. Jun et al. [4,5] considered the fuzzification of interior ideals in semigroups and the notion of an intuitionistic fuzzy interior ideal of a semigroup S , and its properties were investigated. Kuroki [8] discussed some properties of fuzzy ideals and fuzzy bi-ideals in the semigroup. Jun et al. [6] considered the fuzzification of (1,2)-ideals in semigroups and investigated its properties. Yager [9,10] introduced the Pythagorean fuzzy set as a generalization of the fuzzy set. After its existence, several researchers also studied the properties of fuzzy ideals of the semigroup. Yager and Abbasov [37] initiated the notion of Pythagorean fuzzy set and this concept could be considered as a successful generalization of intuitionistic fuzzy sets. The main difference between intuitionistic fuzzy sets and Pythagorean fuzzy sets is that, in the latter case, the sum of membership and non-membership grades is greater than 1, however, the sum of their squares belongs to the unit interval $[0,1]$. Analogously, in this novel pattern, the associated uncertainty of membership grade and non-membership grade can be explained in a valuable method that than of intuitionistic fuzzy set. Gun et al. [7] introduced the new concept of spherical fuzzy

set and discuss the new operations. Smarandache [13] introduced the new concept of neutrosophic set. Khan et.al [12] introduced the Neutrosophic N-Structures and their application in semigroups. The neutrosophic theories have received greater attention in recent years [14]-[32]. Abdel-Basset et al. [33] proposed a new hybrid multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) using Analytical Hierarchy Process(AHP) and Preference Ranking Organization Method for Enrichment Evaluations (PROMETHEE)-II approach for optimal offshore wind power station location selection. Abdel-Basset et al. [34] Provided a neutrosophic PROMETHEE technique for MCDM problems to describe fuzzy information efficiently. Abdel-Basset et al. [35] discussed how smart internet of things technology can assist medical staff in monitoring the spread of COVID-19. Abdel-Basset et al. [36] studied a comprehensive evaluation of the sustainability of hydrogen production options through the use of a MCDM model.

In this paper, we discuss the properties of Pythagorean neutrosophic ideals in semigroups.

2. Preliminaries

Definition 2.1. [3] Let S be a semigroup. M and N be subsets of S , the product of M and N is defined as $MN = \{mn \in S \mid m \in M \text{ and } n \in N\}$ A non- empty subset M of S is called a sub-semigroup of S if $MM \subseteq M$. A non-empty subset M of S is called a left (resp. right) ideal of S if $SM \subseteq M$ (resp. $MS \subseteq M$). M is called a two sided ideal of S if it is both a left ideal and right ideal of S . A sub- semigroup M of S is called a bi-ideal of S if $MSM \subseteq M$. A sub-semigroup M of S is called a (1,2) ideal of S if $MSM^2 \subseteq M$. A semigroup S is said to be (2,2)- regular if $m \in m^2Sm^2$ for any $m \in S$. A semigroup S is called regular if for each element $m \in S$ there exists $x \in S$ such that $m = mxm$. A semigroup S is said to be completely regular if, for any $m \in S$, there exists $x \in S$ such that $m = mxm$ and $mx = xm$. For a semigroup S , is completely regular if and only if (iff) S is a union of groups iff S is (2,2)-regular. By a fuzzy set μ in a non-empty set S we mean a function $\mu : S \rightarrow [0, 1]$, and the complement of μ , denoted by $\bar{\mu}$, is the fuzzy set in S given by $\bar{\mu}(x) = 1 - \mu(x)$ for all $x \in S$.

Definition 2.2. [9] Let X be a universe of discourse, A **Pythagorean fuzzy set** (PFS) $P = \{z, \vartheta_p(x), \omega_p(x)/z \in X\}$ where $\vartheta : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\omega : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ represent the degree of membership and non-membership of the object $z \in X$ to the set P subset to the condition $0 \leq (\vartheta_p(z))^2 + (\omega_p(z))^2 \leq 1$ for all $z \in X$. For the sake of simplicity a PFS is denoted as $P = (\vartheta_p(z), \omega_p(z))$.

Definition 2.3. [13] Let X be a universe of discourse, A **Neutrosophic set** (NS) $N = \{z, \vartheta_N(z), \omega_N(z), \psi_N(z)/z \in X\}$ where $\vartheta : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\omega : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\psi : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ represent the degree of truth membership, indeterminacy-membership and false-membership of the object $z \in X$ to the set N subset to the condition $0 \leq (\vartheta_N(z))^2 + (\omega_N(z))^2 + (\psi_N(z))^2 \leq 3$ for all $z \in X$. For the sake of simplicity a NS is denoted as $N = (\vartheta_N(z), \omega_N(z), \psi_N(z))$.

3. Pythagorean neutrosophic set

Definition 3.1. Let X be a universe of discourse, A **Pythagorean neutrosophic set** (PNS) $P_N = \{z, \mu_p(z), \zeta_p(z), \psi_p(z)/z \in X\}$ where $\mu : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$, $\zeta : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\psi : X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ represent the degree of membership, non-membership and indeterminacy of the object $z \in X$ to the set P_N subset to the condition $0 \leq (\mu_p(z))^2 + (\zeta_p(z))^2 + (\psi_p(z))^2 \leq 2$ for all $z \in X$. For the sake of simplicity a PNS is denoted as $P_N = (\mu_p(z), \zeta_p(z), \psi_p(z))$.

Definition 3.2. Let X be a nonempty set and I the unit interval $[0, 1]$. A Pythagorean neutrosophic set with neutrosophic components [PNS] P_{N_1} and P_{N_2} of the form $P_{N_1} = (z, \mu_{p_1}(z), \zeta_{p_1}(z), \psi_{p_1}(z)/z \in X)$ and $P_{N_2} = (z, \mu_{p_2}(z), \zeta_{p_2}(z), \psi_{p_2}(z)/z \in X)$. Then

- 1) $P_{N_1}^c = (z, \psi_{p_1}(z), \zeta_{p_1}(z), \mu_{p_1}(z)/z \in X)$
- 2) $P_{N_1} \cup P_{N_2} = \{z, \max(\mu_{P_1}(z), \mu_{P_2}(z)), \max(\zeta_{P_1}(z), \zeta_{P_2}(z)), \min(\psi_{P_1}(z), \psi_{P_2}(z))/z \in X\}$
- 3) $P_{N_1} \cap P_{N_2} = \{z, \min(\mu_{P_1}(z), \mu_{P_2}(z)), \min(\zeta_{P_1}(z), \zeta_{P_2}(z)), \max(\psi_{P_1}(z), \psi_{P_2}(z))/z \in X\}$

4. Pythagorean neutrosophic ideals in semigroups

In this section, let S denote a semigroup unless otherwise specified. We discuss the details of Pythagorean neutrosophic ideals in semigroups.

Definition 4.1. A Pythagorean neutrosophic (PNS) $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ in S is called an Pythagorean neutrosophic sub-semigroup of S , if

- (i) $\mu_p(x_1x_2) \leq \max\{\mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2)\}$
- (ii) $\zeta_p(x_1x_2) \geq \max\{\zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2)\}$
- (iii) $\psi_p(x_1x_2) \leq \max\{\psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2)\}$ for all $x_1, x_2 \in S$.

Definition 4.2. A PNS $P = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ in S is called an Pythagorean neutrosophic left ideal of S , if

- (i) $\mu_p(x_1x_2) \leq \mu_p(x_2)$
- (ii) $\zeta_p(x_1x_2) \geq \zeta_p(x_2)$
- (iii) $\psi_p(x_1x_2) \leq \psi_p(x_2)$ for all $x_1, x_2 \in S$.

A Pythagorean neutrosophic right ideal of S is defined in an analogous way. An PNS $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ in S is called an Pythagorean neutrosophic ideal of S , if it is both a Pythagorean neutrosophic left and Pythagorean neutrosophic right ideal of S . It is clear that any Pythagorean neutrosophic left (resp. right) ideal of S is a Pythagorean neutrosophic sub-semigroup of S .

Definition 4.3. A Pythagorean neutrosophic sub-semigroup $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ of S is called an Pythagorean neutrosophic bi-ideal (PNBI) of S .

- (i) $\mu_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \max\{\mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2)\}$

- (ii) $\zeta_p(x_1ux_2) \geq \max \{\zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2)\}$
- (ii) $\psi_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \max \{\psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2)\}$ for all $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$.

Theorem 4.4. *If $\{P_i\}_{i \in I}$ is a family of PNBI of S , then $\cap P_i$ is an PNBI of S . Where*

$$\cap P_i = (\vee \mu_{p_i}, \vee \zeta_{p_i}, \vee \psi_{p_i}) \text{ and } \vee \mu_{p_i} = \sup \{\mu_{p_i}(x_1) | i \in I, x_1 \in S\},$$

$$\vee \zeta_{p_i} = \sup \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_1) | i \in I, x_1 \in S\}, \vee \psi_{p_i} = \sup \{\psi_{p_i}(x_1) | i \in I, x_1 \in S\}.$$

Proof. Let $x_1, x_2 \in S$. Then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1x_2) &\leq \vee \{\max \{\mu_{p_i}(x_1), \mu_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\mu_{p_i}(x_1), \mu_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\mu_{p_i}(x_1)\}, \max \{\mu_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1), \vee \mu_{p_i}(x_2)\} \\ \vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_1x_2) &\geq \vee \{\max \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_1), \zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_1), \zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_1)\}, \max \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\wedge \zeta_{p_i}(x_1), \wedge \zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\} \\ \vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1x_2) &\leq \vee \{\max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_1), \psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_1), \psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_1)\}, \max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1), \vee \psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\cap P_i$ is an Pythagorean neutrosophic sub-semigroup of S .

Next for $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1ux_2) &\leq \vee \{\min \{\mu_{p_i}(x_1), \mu_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\mu_{p_i}(x_1), \mu_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\mu_{p_i}(x_1)\}, \max \{\mu_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1), \vee \mu_{p_i}(x_2)\} \\ \vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_1ux_2) &\geq \vee \{\min \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_1), \zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_1), \zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_1)\}, \max \{\zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_1), \vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_2)\} \\ \vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1ux_2) &\leq \vee \{\max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_1), \psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_1), \psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_1)\}, \max \{\psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}\} \\ &= \max \{\vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1), \vee \psi_{p_i}(x_2)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\cap P_i$ is an PNBI of S .

This completes the proof. \square

Theorem 4.5. *Every Pythagorean neutrosophic left(right) ideal of S is an Pythagorean neutrosophic bi-ideal of S .*

Proof. Let $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is a Pythagorean neutrosophic left ideal of S and $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_p(x_1ux_2) &= \mu_p(x_1ux_2) \\ &\leq \mu_p(x_2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\mu_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \max\{\mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_p(x_1ux_2) &= \zeta_p(x_1ux_2) \\ &\geq \zeta_p(x_2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\zeta_p(x_1ux_2) \geq \max\{\zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2)\}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\psi_p(x_1ux_2) &= \psi_p(x_1ux_2) \\ &\leq \psi_p(x_2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\psi_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \max\{\psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2)\}$$

Thus $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is PNBI of S .

The right case is provided in an analogous way. \square

Theorem 4.6. *Every Pythagorean neutrosophic bi-ideal of a group S is constant.*

Proof. Let $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ be an PNBI of a group S and let x_1 be any element of S .

Then

$$\begin{aligned}\mu_p(x_1) &= \mu_p(ex_1e) \\ &\leq \max\{\mu_p(e), \mu_p(e)\} \\ &= \mu_p(e) \\ &= \mu_p(ee) \\ &= \mu_p(x_1x_1^{-1})(x_1^{-1}x_1) \\ &= \mu_p(x_1(x_1^{-1}x_1^{-1})x_1) \\ &\leq \max\{\mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_1)\} \\ &= \mu_p(x_1)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\zeta_p(x_1) &= \zeta_p(ex_1e) \\ &\geq \max\{\zeta_p(e), \zeta_p(e)\} \\ &= \zeta_p(e) \\ &= \zeta_p(ee) \\ &= \zeta_p(x_1x_1^{-1})(x_1^{-1}x_1) \\ &= \zeta_p(x_1(x_1^{-1}x_1^{-1})x_1) \\ &\geq \max\{\zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_1)\} \\ &= \zeta_p(x_1)\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi_p(x_1) &= \psi_p(ex_1e) \\
&\leq \max\{\psi_p(e), \psi_p(e)\} \\
&= \psi_p(e) \\
&= \psi_p(ee) \\
&= \psi_p(x_1x_1^{-1})(x_1^{-1}x_1) \\
&= \psi_p(x_1(x_1^{-1}x_1^{-1})x_1) \\
&\leq \max\{\psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_1)\} \\
&= \psi_p(x_1).
\end{aligned}$$

Where e is the identity of S . It follows that $\mu_p(x_1) = \mu_p(e)$, $\zeta_p(x_1) = \zeta_p(e)$ and $\psi_p(x_1) = \psi_p(e)$ which means that $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is constant. \square

Theorem 4.7. *If an PNS $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ in S is an PNBI of S , then so is $\square P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \bar{\psi}_p)$.*

Proof. It is sufficient to show that $\bar{\psi}_p$ satisfies the conditions in Definition 3.1 and Definition 3.4. For any $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{\psi}_p(x_1x_2) &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1x_2) \\
&\leq 1 - \min\{\psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2)\} \\
&= \max\{1 - \psi_p(x_1), 1 - \psi_p(x_2)\} \\
&= \max\{\bar{\psi}_p(x_1), \bar{\psi}_p(x_2)\}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\bar{\psi}_p(x_1ux_2) &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1ux_2) \\
&\leq 1 - \min\{\psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2)\} \\
&= \max\{1 - \psi_p(x_1), 1 - \psi_p(x_2)\} \\
&= \max\{\bar{\psi}_p(x_1), \bar{\psi}_p(x_2)\}.
\end{aligned}$$

Therefore $\square P_N$ is an PNBI of S . \square

Definition 4.8. A Pythagorean neutrosophic sub-semigroup $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ of S is called a Pythagorean neutrosophic (1,2) ideal of S . If

- (i) $\mu_p(x_1u(x_2x_3)) \leq \max\{\mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2), \mu_p(x_3)\}$
- (ii) $\zeta_p(x_1u(x_2x_3)) \geq \max\{\zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2), \zeta_p(x_3)\}$
- (iii) $\psi_p(x_1u(x_2x_3)) \leq \max\{\psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2), \psi_p(x_3)\}$ $u, x_1, x_2, x_3 \in S$.

Theorem 4.9. *Every PNBI is a Pythagorean neutrosophic (1,2) ideal of S .*

Proof. Let PNS $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ be an PNBI of S and let $u, x_1, x_2, x_3 \in S$.

Then

$$\mu_p(x_1u(x_2x_3)) = \mu_p((x_1ux_2)x_3)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&\leq \max \{ \mu_p(x_1 u x_2), \mu_p(x_3) \} \\
&\leq \max \{ \max \{ \mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2) \}, \mu_p(x_3) \} \\
&= \max \{ \mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2), \mu_p(x_3) \} \\
\zeta_p(x_1 u(x_2 x_3)) &= \zeta_p((x_1 u x_2) x_3) \\
&\geq \max \{ \zeta_p(x_1 u x_2), \zeta_p(x_3) \} \\
&\geq \max \{ \max \{ \zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2) \}, \zeta_p(x_3) \} \\
&= \max \{ \zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2), \zeta_p(x_3) \}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi_p(x_1 u(x_2 x_3)) &= \psi_p((x_1 u x_2) x_3) \\
&\leq \max \{ \psi_p(x_1 u x_2), \psi_p(x_3) \} \\
&\leq \max \{ \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \}, \psi_p(x_3) \} \\
&= \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2), \psi_p(x_3) \}.
\end{aligned}$$

Hence $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is a Pythagorean neutrosophic (1,2) ideal of S . \square

To consider the converse of theorem next theorem, we need to strengthen the condition of a semigroup S .

Theorem 4.10. *If S is a regular semigroup, then every Pythagorean neutrosophic (1,2) ideal of S is an PNBI of S .*

Proof. Assume that a semigroup S is regular and let $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ be an Pythagorean neutrosophic (1,2) ideal of S . Let $u, x_1, x_2, x_3 \in S$. Since S is regular, we have $x_1 u \in (x_1 S x_1) S \subseteq x_1 S x_1$, which implies that $x_1 u = x_1 s x_1$ for some $s \in S$.

Thus

$$\begin{aligned}
\mu_p(x_1 u x_2) &= \mu_p((x_1 s x_1) x_2) \\
&= \mu_p(x_1 s(x_1 x_2)) \\
&\leq \max \{ \mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2) \} \\
&= \max \{ \mu_p(x_1), \mu_p(x_2) \} \\
\zeta_p(x_1 u x_2) &= \zeta_p((x_1 s x_1) x_2) \\
&= \zeta_p(x_1 s(x_1 x_2)) \\
&\geq \max \{ \zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2) \} \\
&= \max \{ \zeta_p(x_1), \zeta_p(x_2) \}
\end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}
\psi_p(x_1 u x_2) &= \psi_p((x_1 s x_1) x_2) \\
&= \psi_p(x_1 s(x_1 x_2)) \\
&\leq \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \}
\end{aligned}$$

$$= \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \}.$$

Therefore $P_N = (\zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is PNBI of S . \square

Theorem 4.11. A PNS $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is an PNBI of S if and only if μ_p , ζ_p and $\overline{\psi_p}$ are FBI of S .

Proof. Let $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ be an PNBI of S . Then clearly μ_p is a FBI of S . Let $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\psi_p}(x_1x_2) &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1x_2) \\ &\geq 1 - \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ (1 - \psi_p(x_1)), (1 - \psi_p(x_2)) \} \\ &= \min \{ \overline{\psi_p}(x_1), \overline{\psi_p}(x_2) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \overline{\psi_p}(x_1ux_2) &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1ux_2) \\ &\geq 1 - \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ (1 - \psi_p(x_1)), (1 - \psi_p(x_2)) \} \\ &= \min \{ \overline{\psi_p}(x_1), \overline{\psi_p}(x_2) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\overline{\psi_p}$ is a fuzzy bi-ideal of S .

Conversely, suppose that ζ_p and $\overline{\psi_p}$ are FBI of S . Let $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \psi_p(x_1x_2) &= \overline{\psi_p}(x_1x_2) \\ &\leq \min \{ \overline{\psi_p}(x_1), \overline{\psi_p}(x_2) \} \\ &= \min \{ (1 - \psi_p(x_1)), (1 - \psi_p(x_2)) \} \\ &= \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \} \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 1 - \psi_p(x_1ux_2) &= \overline{\psi_p}(x_1ux_2) \\ &\geq \min \{ \overline{\psi_p}(x_1), \overline{\psi_p}(x_2) \} \\ &= 1 - \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \}. \end{aligned}$$

Which implies that $\psi_p(x_1x_2) \leq \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \}$ and $\psi_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \max \{ \psi_p(x_1), \psi_p(x_2) \}$

This completes the proof. \square

Definition 4.12. A PNS $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ in S is called an Pythagorean neutrosophic interior ideal(PNII) of S if it satisfies

- (i) $\mu_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \mu_p(u)$
- (ii) $\zeta_p(x_1ux_2) \geq \zeta_p(u)$
- (iii) $\psi_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \psi_p(u)$ $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$.

Theorem 4.13. If $\{P_i\}_{i \in I}$ is a family of PNII of S , then $\cap P_i$ is a PNII of S . Where $\cap P_i =$

$$\begin{aligned} (\vee \mu_{p_i}, \vee \zeta_{p_i}, \vee \psi_{p_i}) \text{ and } \vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1) &= \sup \{ \mu_{p_i}(x_1) | i \in I, x_1 \in S \}, \\ \vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_1) &= \sup \{ \zeta_{p_i}(x_1) | i \in I, x_1 \in S \}, \vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1) = \sup \{ \psi_{p_i}(x_1) | i \in I, x_1 \in S \}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Let $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$.

Then

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1x_2) &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \mu_{p_i}(x_1), \mu_{p_i}(x_2) \} \} \\ &= (\vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1)) \vee (\vee \mu_{p_i}(x_2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_1x_2) &\geq \max \{ \max \{ \zeta_{p_i}(x_1), \zeta_{p_i}(x_2) \} \} \\ &= (\vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_1)) \vee (\vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_2)) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1x_2) &\leq \max \{ \max \{ \psi_{p_i}(x_1), \psi_{p_i}(x_2) \} \} \\ &= (\vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1)) \vee (\vee \psi_{p_i}(x_2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\vee \mu_{p_i}(x_1ux_2) \leq \vee \mu_{p_i}(u)$$

$$\vee \zeta_{p_i}(x_1ux_2) \geq \vee \zeta_{p_i}(u)$$

and

$$\vee \psi_{p_i}(x_1ux_2) \leq \vee \psi_{p_i}(u).$$

Hence $\cap P_i$ is an PNII of S . \square

Definition 4.14. Let $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is a PNS of S and let $\alpha \in [0, 1]$ then the sets.

$\mu_{p,\alpha} = \{x_1 \in S : \mu_p(x_1)\alpha\}$, $\zeta_{p,\alpha} = \{x_1 \in S : \zeta_p(x_1)\alpha\}$ and $\psi_{p,\alpha} = \{x_1 \in S : \psi_p(x_1)\alpha\}$ are called a μ_p -level α -cut, ζ_p -level α -cut and ψ_p -level α -cut of K respectively.

Theorem 4.15. If an PNS $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ in S is an PNII of S , then the μ -level α -cut $\mu_{p,\alpha}$, ζ -level α -cut $\zeta_{p,\alpha}$ and ψ -level α -cut $\psi_{p,\alpha}$ of P_N are interior ideal of S , for every $\alpha \in Im(\mu_p) \cap Im(\zeta_p) \cap Im(\psi_p) \subseteq [0, 1]$.

Proof. Let $\alpha \in Im(\mu_p) \cap Im(\zeta_p) \cap Im(\psi_p) \subseteq [0, 1]$.

let $x_1, x_2 \in \mu_{p,\alpha}$ then $\mu_p(x_1) \leq \alpha$ and $\mu_p(x_2) \leq \alpha$. It follows from that

$$\mu_p(x_1x_2) \leq \mu_p(x_1) \vee \mu_p(x_2) \leq \alpha. \text{ So that } x_1, x_2 \in \mu_{p,\alpha}.$$

If $x_1, x_2 \in \zeta_{p,\alpha}$ then $\zeta_p(x_1) \geq \alpha$ and $\zeta_p(x_2) \geq \alpha$. It follows from that.

$$\zeta_p(x_1x_2) \geq \zeta_p(x_1) \vee \zeta_p(x_2) \geq \alpha. \text{ So that } x_1, x_2 \in \zeta_{p,\alpha}.$$

If $x_1, x_2 \in \psi_{p,\alpha}$, then $\psi_p(x_1) \leq \alpha$ and $\psi_p(x_2) \leq \alpha$ and so $\psi_p(x_1x_2) \leq \psi_p(x_1) \vee \psi_p(x_2) \leq \alpha$,

that is $x_1, x_2 \in \psi_{p,\alpha}$.

Hence $\mu_{p,\alpha}$, $\zeta_{p,\alpha}$ and $\psi_{p,\alpha}$ are sub-semigroup of S . Now let $x_1x_2 \in S$ and $u \in \mu_{p,\alpha}$. Then $\mu_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \mu_p(u) \leq \alpha$ and so $x_1ux_2 \in \mu_{p,\alpha}$.

If $u \in \zeta_{p,\alpha}$. Then $\zeta_p(x_1ux_2) \geq \zeta_p(u) \geq \alpha$ and so $x_1ux_2 \in \zeta_{p,\alpha}$.

If $u \in \psi_{p,\alpha}$. Then $\psi_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \psi_p(u) \leq \alpha$ thus $x_1ux_2 \in \psi_{p,\alpha}$.

Therefore $\mu_{p,\alpha}, \zeta_{p,\alpha}$ and $\psi_{p,\alpha}$ are interior ideal of S . \square

Theorem 4.16. A PNS $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ is and PNII of S if and only if $\mu_p, \zeta_p, \bar{\psi}_p$ are fuzzy interior ideal (FII) of S .

Proof. Let $P_N = (\mu_p, \zeta_p, \psi_p)$ be an PNII of S . Then clearly μ_p is FII of S . Let $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$. Then

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{\psi_p}(x_1x_2) &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1x_2) \\ &\geq 1 - (\psi_p(x_1) \vee \psi_p(x_2)) \\ &= (1 - \psi_p(x_1)) \wedge (1 - \psi_p(x_2)) \\ &= \overline{\psi_k}(x_1) \wedge \overline{\psi_p}(x_2)\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}\overline{\psi_p}(x_1ux_2) &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1ux_2) \\ &\geq 1 - (\psi_p(u)) \\ &= \overline{\psi_p}(u)\end{aligned}$$

$\overline{\psi_k}$ is a FII of S .

Conversely.

Suppose that ζ_p and $\overline{\psi_p}$ are FII of S . Let $u, x_1, x_2 \in S$.

$$\begin{aligned}1 - \psi_p(x_1x_2) &= \overline{\psi_p}(x_1x_2) \\ &\geq \overline{\psi_p}(x_1) \wedge \overline{\psi_p}(x_2) \\ &= (1 - \psi_p(x_1)) \wedge (1 - \psi_p(x_2)) \\ &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1) \vee \psi_p(x_2) \\ &= 1 - \psi_p(x_1ux_2) = \overline{\psi_p}(x_1ux_2) \\ &\geq \overline{\psi_p}(u) = 1 - \psi_p(u)\end{aligned}$$

which implies $\psi_p(x_1x_2) \leq \psi_p(x_1) \vee \psi_p(x_2)$

and

$$\psi_p(x_1ux_2) \leq \psi_p(u)$$

This completes the proof. \square

5. Conclusions

In this paper Pythagorean neutrosophic sub-semigroup, Pythagorean neutrosophic left(resp.right) ideal, Pythagorean neutrosophic ideal, Pythagorean neutrosophic bi-ideal, Pythagorean neutrosophic interior ideal and investigated some properties.

References

1. Atanassov, K.T. Intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Fuzzy Sets and System, 1986; Volume 20, pp.87–96.
2. Atanassov, K.T. New operations defined over the intuitionistic fuzzy sets. Fuzzy Sets and Systems, 1994; Volume 61, pp. 137–142.
3. Chinnadurai, V. Fuzzy ideals in algebraic structures. Lap Lambert Academic Publishing, 2013.
4. Jun, Y.B.; Kim, K.H. Intuitionistic fuzzy interior ideals of semigroups. Int. J. Math. Sci., 2001; Volume 27, pp. 261–267.
5. Jun, Y.B.; Kim, K.H. Intuitionistic fuzzy ideals of semigroups. Indian J. Pure Appl. Math., 2002; Volume 33, pp. 443–449.
6. Jun, Y.B.; Lajos, S. On fuzzy (1,2)-ideals of semigroups. P.U.M.A., 1997; Volume 8, pp. 335–338.

7. Gundogdu, F.K.; Kahraman, C. Properties and Arithmetic Operations of spherical fuzzy subsets. *Studies in Fuzziness and Soft Computing*, 2018; pp. 3–25.
8. Kuroki, N. On fuzzy ideals and fuzzy bi-ideals in semigroups. *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 1981; Volume 5, pp. 203–215.
9. Yager, R.R. Pythagorean fuzzy subsets. In: *Proc. Joint IFSA World Congress and NAFIPS Annual Meeting*, Edmonton, Canada, 2013; pp. 57–61.
10. Yager, R.R. Pythagorean membership grades in multicriteria decision making. *IEEE Transaction on Fuzzy Systems*, 2014; Volume 22, pp. 958–965.
11. Zadeh, L. A. *Fuzzy Sets*. *Information and Control*, 1965; Volume 8, pp. 338–353.
12. Khan, M.S.; Anis; Smarandache, F.; Jun, Y.B. Neutrosophic N-structures and their applications in semi-groups. *Annals of Fuzzy Mathematics and Informatics*, reprint.
13. Smarandache, F. *A Unifying Field in Logics. Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic Probability, Set and Logic*. American Research Press, Rehoboth, Mass, USA, 1999.
14. Smarandache, F. Neutrosophic set, a generalisation of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets. *Inter. J. Pure Appl. Math.*, 2005; Volume 24, pp. 287-297.
15. Chinnadurai, V.; Smarandache, F.; Bobin, A. Multi-Aspect Decision-Making Process in Equity Investment Using Neutrosophic Soft Matrices. *Neutrosophic sets and systems*, 2020; Volume 31(1), pp. 224–241.
16. Zhang, Z.; Wu, C. A Novel Method for Single-valued Neutrosophic Multi-Criteria Decision Making with Incomplete Weight Information. *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2014; Volume 4, pp.35–49.
17. Wei, G.; Zhang, Z. Some single-valued neutrosophic Bonferroni power aggregation operators in multiple attribute decision making. *J Ambient Intell Humaniz Comput.*, 2019; Volume 10, pp. 863-882.
18. Wang, H.; Smarandache, F.; Zhang, Y.Q.; Sunderraman, R. Single valued neutrosophic sets. *Multispace Multistruct* 2010; Volume 4, pp. 410-413.
19. Wang, H.; Smarandache, F.; Zhang, Y.; Sunderraman, R. Single Valued Neutrosophic Sets. In: *Proceedings of 10th International Conference on Fuzzy Theory and Technology*, Salt Lake City, Utah (2005).
20. Wang, H.; Smarandache, F.; Zhang, Y.Q.; Sunderraman, R. *Interval Neutrosophic Sets and Logic: Theory and Applications in Computing*, Hexis, AZ 2005.
21. Bhowmik, M., and Pal, M., Intuitionistic neutrosophic set, *Journal of Information and Computing Science*, 2009; Volume 4(2), pp. 142–152.
22. Zhang, H.; Wang, J.; Chen, X. An outranking approach for multicriteria decision-making problems with interval-valued neutrosophic sets. *Neural Comput Appl.*, 2016; Volume 27(3), pp. 615-627.
23. Broumi, S.; Smarandache, F. Intuitionistic Neutrosophic Soft Set. 2013; Volume 8(2), pp.130–140.
24. Broumi, S.; Generalized Neutrosophic Soft Set. *International Journal of Computer Science, Engineering and Information Technology (IJCSEIT)*, 2013; Volume 3(2).
25. Peng, J.J.; Wang, J.Q.; Zhang, H.Y.; Chen, X.H. An outranking approach for multi-criteria decision-making problems with simplified neutrosophic sets. *Appl. Soft Comput.*, 2014, Volume 25 pp. 336-346.
26. Ye, J. Multicriteria decision-making method using the correlation coefficient under single-valued neutrosophic environment. *Int. J. Gen Syst.*, 2013; Volume 42(4), pp. 386-394.
27. Ye, J. A multicriteria decision-making method using aggregation operators for simplified neutrosophic sets. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.*, 2014a; Volume 26, pp. 2459-2466.
28. Ye, J. Similarity measures between interval neutrosophic sets and their applications in multicriteria decision-making. *J. Intell. Fuzzy Syst.*, 2014b; Volume 26(1), pp. 165-172.
29. Ye, J. Single valued neutrosophic cross-entropy for multicriteria decision making problems. *Appl. Math. Model*, 2014c; Volume 38(3), pp. 1170-1175.
30. Nancy; Garg, H. Single-valued neutrosophic Entropy of order alpha. *Neutrosophic Sets and System*, 2016a; Volume 14, pp. 21-28.

31. Nancy; Garg, H. An improved score function for ranking neutrosophic sets and its application to decision-making process. *Int. J. Uncertain Quan*, 2016b; Volume 6(5), pp. 377-385.
32. Nancy; Garg, H. Novel single-valued neutrosophic decision making operators under Frank norm operations and its application. *Int. J. Uncertain Quan*, 2016c; Volume 6(4), pp. 361-375.
33. Abdel-Basset, M.; Gamal, A.; Chakarbortty, R.; Rayan, M.A. A new hybrid multi-criteria decision approach for location selection of sustainable off shore wind energy stations:A case study. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 280, pp. 124462.
34. Abdel-Basset, M.; Manogaran, M.; Mohamed, M.; Rayan, M.A. A neutrosophic theory based security approach for fog and mobile-edge computing. *Computer Networks*, Volume 157, pp. 122–132.
35. Abdel-Basset, M.; Mohamed, M.; Elhoseny, M. (?*covid19*?) A model for the effective COVID-19 identification in uncertainty environment using primary symptoms and CT scans. *Health Information journal*, 2020, 1460458220952918.
36. Abdel-Basset, M.; Gamal, A.; Chakarbortty, R.; Rayan, M.A. Evaluation of sustainable hydrogen production options using an advanced hybrid MCDM approach: A case study. *International Journal of Hydrogen Energy*, 2020.
37. Yager, R.R.; Abbasov, A.M; Pythagorean membership grades, complex numbers, and decision making. *Int. J. Intell. Syst.*, 2013, Volume 28, pp.436–452.

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